

A Study on the Relationship between Working Environment and Labor Unrest in Ready-Made Garment (RMG) Industry of Bangladesh.

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Mohammad Ishtiaq Uddin**-Assistant Professor Department of Business Administration-University of Asia Pacific

⁽²⁾ **Sadia Tangem**-Assistant Professor-Department of Business Administration University of Asia Pacific

Abstract

Over 80% of export earnings are come from ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh. Basically, this sector is the key base of foreign earnings and as well as for employment generation to the economic development of a nation as a whole. About more than 5 million workers are involved in this sector of Bangladesh. In recent years, this sector is facing serious disturbances from workers due to unwelcomed working environment which are created a serious bad image to the international buyers. Keeping this concern, the study is try to find out the relationship between labor unrest and working environment of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh. A total of 80 workers were selected through simple random sampling technique (lottery method). To collect primary data a well structured and close-ended questionnaire has been used. The data were analyzed and interpreted using linear regression, coefficient analysis and SPSS 16.0 to serve the purpose of the study. The study concluded with the observation that majority of the respondents give emphasis on unjust payment behavior, absence of proper infrastructural facilities, absence of proper recreation facilities and mental harassment. If the government and authority of garments sector in Bangladesh work over these issues seriously then it will be easily eliminated.

Introduction

Bangladesh is a country of huge opportunities for the existence of different potential industries and ready-made garments (RMG) are the most lucrative one. At present, it brings huge export earnings and these earnings are growing at a fanatic pace which is helping to create a strong industrial base for economic contribution and employment generation all together. The most important aspects of ready-made garments in Bangladesh are women employment generation and congenial working atmosphere. These two factors especially supported Bangladesh to advance in global arenas of garments sector. Even, other potential manufacturing sectors grow of a progressing garments industry (Mohammad Ismail Bhuiyan, 2013).

Regardless of having an extraordinary performance, the ready-made garments (RMG) sectors have been facing various problems including a major problem called labor unrest. It is now a growing phenomenon for this sector which is seriously ignored by the top management of garments industry in Bangladesh. This is causing especially due to congenial working atmosphere (unjust & irregular mode of payment, absence of good physical infrastructures, mental & physical harassment and discrimination on the basis of gender perspectives) that seriously impacts sound barriers to the productivity of garments. When the workers are not getting the above key prerequisites in usual ways, they are walking on streets and create destructive works to fulfill their required demands which is ultimately damaging their relationships with owner of garments (Mohammad Ismail Bhuiyan, 2013). So, this paper is tries to analyze the relationship between working conditions and labor unrest of ready-made garments (RMG) sector in Bangladesh for smoothing the economic base of this sector in local as well as in international market.

Literature review

Labor unrest in ready-made garment industries in Bangladesh became very common incidents in recent years between management and workers due to poor working conditions and other related issues which are posing a serious threat for the advancement of this sector. But, what is labor unrest and how it is related to working conditions? Labor unrest is an organizing effort undertaken by labor unions especially where labor disputes become violent which obstruct the normal process of business. Basically, labor unrest is occurred when the work-force or labor force is depressed with not fulfilling their basic needs from the authority or top management. According to Jakir (2010) absence of basic human needs often workers compel to pursue them the path of violent behavior. Sometimes, it is more than worse a life of a prisoner in Bangladesh. It is now a necessity for continuous discussion between management and workers, mainly in terms of changing working atmosphere (CPD, Bangladesh). Working atmosphere has a number of facets which includes unjust payment behavior, absence of proper infrastructural & recreation facilities, mental and physical harassment and discrimination on the basis of gender perspectives. The unwelcome working atmosphere of garment workers have been emphasized by the recent incident called Rana Plaza collapse and another terrific incident called fire at Tazreen factory in December 2012 (Miller, 2012). These incidents indicate that there is occurred no

improvement in building infrastructures which causes a serious violation in terms of building code standards in Bangladesh (Nazneen Ahmed and Dev Nathan, 2014).

One study shows that workers are not satisfied because of salary management behavior of authority (Abrar Ahmed Apu, 2007; Sirajul Islam and Sonia Ahmad, 2010). Therefore, this kind of dissatisfaction is prevailing along with workers that lead them to follow the path of unrest in this potential sector (Nazrul Islam and Shaheen Ahmed, 2014).

Another study shows that unjust payment system is also the major cause of labor unrest in this sector (Absar, 2001). According to Islam and Ahmed (2010) the privilege and rights of workers are also ignored by the top authority in the garments sector of Bangladesh and they are rarely followed the labor laws and other international conventions in case of labor welfare (Islam and Ahmed, 2010).

High discrimination in terms of wage between employees and workers is another major root to unrest in the manufacturing environment in the garments sector of Bangladesh (Apu, 2010). Basically, it's a fundamental part for all conflicts in ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh (Mohammad Ismail Bhuiyan, 2013).

Lack of recreation facilities is another major reason for labor unrest (Paul-Majumder, 2007). It is viewed that the workers are involved in their activities for all day long without any reasonable time-break (Nazrul Islam and Shaheen Ahmed, 2014).

Mohammad Ismail Bhuiyan (2013) acknowledged that a conflict is placed at Narayanganj on September 22, 2011 between management and workers due to irregularities in financial issues and last but not least, end of harassment of workers. At least 10 peoples including journalist were injured in that clash.

A study carried out by BIDS pointed out that sometimes the gender differentiation impacts in the ready-made garments industries of Bangladesh. They found that women workers cannot obtain the full advantage because of discrimination of gender aspects which may them dissatisfied (Majumder and Begum, 2006). Sometimes, it may convert into a conflict against their male counterpart as well as male counterpart of management which is eventually leaded to the serious unrest in this sector.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to identify to what extent labor unrest is related to the working conditions of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh and the specific objectives are:

- a) To determine various factors of working conditions that might influence the labor unrest of RMG sector in Bangladesh.
- b) To identify the most influential factors of working conditions that has a positive relationship with labor unrest of RMG sector in Bangladesh.
- c) To suggest some possible avenues in regard to overcome labor unrest by making the working environment better of RMG sector in Bangladesh.

Hypotheses of the study

Is there any relation between labor unrest and working environment of ready-made garments (RMG) sector in Bangladesh? To test this research question, following null and alternative hypothesis are designed.

Ho: There is no relationship between labor unrest and working environment of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh.

H1: There is a relationship between labor unrest and working environment of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

The present study has been conducted to analyze the relationship between labor unrest and working environment of ready-made garments (RMG) sector in Bangladesh. This study is a quantitative research which is arranged through a survey strategy. To conduct this study both primary and secondary data have been used. The primary data has been collected using a structured questionnaire having MCQ and 7 featured likert scale on the basis of the objectives of the study and the secondary has been collected from relevant websites, articles and publications. 5 (five) garments have been randomly selected concerning labor unrest & working environment and among those garments labors from different units have been chosen.

The target population of this study covers labors of different ready-made garments of different units in Bangladesh. The sampling frame of this study covers labors of different ready-made garments of different areas in Dhaka division. The sample size is 80 (n=80) considering 99% incidence rate and 95% completion rate. The sampling technique used in this research was simple random sampling (lottery method) for the selection of ready-made garments and labors and interviewed to serve the purpose. The collected data have been analyzed using Multiple Regression Analysis, coefficient analysis and frequencies using statistical software SPSS 16.

Analysis and Findings of the Study

The study develops six groups of variables influencing labor unrest, namely, unjust payment behavior, absence of proper infrastructural facilities, absence of proper recreation facilities, mental harassment, physical harassment and discrimination on the basis of gender perspectives. The results show that unjust payment behavior, absence of proper infrastructural facilities, absence of proper recreation facilities and mental harassment are highly significant factors affecting the labor unrest of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh. These four factors together explain 85.3% of the total variation of the model. More addition of independent variables will have less impact on adjusted R square which is explained by 84.1%. The multiple coefficient of correlation (R=0.924) indicates that variables chosen are highly correlated and this give the model a good fit. On the other hand, physical harassment and discrimination on the basis of gender perspectives are highly insignificant for determining the labor unrest of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh. [Table 1 and 1(a)]

**Table 1: Relationship between labor unrest and the working environment of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh
Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.924 ^a	.853	.841	.076

a. Predictors: (Constant), Discrimination on the basis of Gender Perspectives, Unjust Payment Behavior, Physical Harrasment, Absence of Proper Recreation Facilities, Mental Harrasment, Absence of Proper Infrastructural Facilities.

Table 1(a): Coefficient Analysis
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.094	.596		.158	.875
Unjust Payment Behavior	.423	.096	.247	4.426	.000
Absence of Proper Infrastructural Facilities	1.019	.086	1.412	11.876	.000
Absence of Proper Recreation Facilities	-.865	.093	-1.102	-9.270	.000
Mental Harrasment	.429	.058	.429	7.374	.000
Physical Harrasment	.003	.009	.014	.294	.769
Discrimination on the basis of Gender Perspectives	-.021	.033	-.031	-.635	.528

a. Dependent Variable: Labor Unrest

Conclusion

Ready-made garments sector is now became a very promising sector in terms of economic contribution and economic generation of a country. Many countries all over the world including the European Union, the United States, Canada and Japan are importing ready-made garments from the Bangladesh (Mohammad Ismail Bhuiyan, 2013). More than 5 million workers are directly depends on this sector. However, this ready-made garments sector has faced enormous difficulties in regard to labor that slow down their growth in local as well as international market. Our research has shown that working environment do favorably influences labor unrest of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh. It is clearly evident from the data that majority of the workers or labors, gave a more scoring reply to the factors such as unjust payment behavior, absence of proper infrastructural facilities, absence of proper recreation facilities and mental harassment are the true influential indicators for labor unrest. Although, it is surprising that some of the respondents point out the term 'labor unrest' most stimulating factor for improving the working environment of this sector in Bangladesh.

Recommendations

1. Implementation of labor rights should be carefully monitored by the garments authority and government for the betterment of their livelihood (Morshed, 2007).
2. Proper reforms in legislation area (Ghosh et al., 2010) are necessary for pleasant-sounding management-worker relationship of ready-made garments sector in Bangladesh.
3. Wages and other benefit issues are needed to be in tune to avoid conflicts between labor and management in this vibrant sector.
4. Garments authority should arrange some interactional programs for workers at all level by giving them realistic awareness (Mohammad Ismail Bhuiyan, 2013) on working environment issues.
5. Partnering is more effective (Ghosh et al., 2010) to blockade the labor unrest in this promising sector.

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